

Transferable Skills – Report 2

Deliverable 2.7

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 2.7 Transferable Skills – Report 2

Version 1

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Table of contents

Executive summary.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Course aims.....	6
3. Learning outcomes	6
4. Course structure	7
5. Learning activities	10
6. Resources.....	17
7. Outputs	17
8. Course evaluation.....	18
Annex 1– Task 1 feedback.....	1
Annex 2– Task 2 feedback.....	3
Annex 3– Evaluation surveys.....	5

Executive summary

This document describes the content and implementation process of the Transferable Skills 2 (TS2) course. It presents the course aims, learning outcomes, structure and content, learning activities, resources, as well the outputs of the course. TS2 is focused on entrepreneurship, and professional and career development. Transferable skills covered under TS2 include eight topics divided into two sub-groups: (a) Entrepreneurship/Enterprise; and (b) Professional and career development. TS2 is a 4-ECTS course, which equates to approximately 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work. TS2 has also two group work tasks.

The document also presents the results of the course evaluation in three settings: at the Workshop 2 in Budapest, at Summer School 2 in Valencia, and overall. There are three Annexes to illustrate the feedback to ESRs on Task 1, feedback to ESRs on Task 2, and the survey results for TS2 at the workshop and summer School.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this report is to document the Transferable Skills 2 (TS2) course in terms of course aims, learning outcomes, structure and content, learning activities, resources, as well as the outputs of the course. TS2 is focused on entrepreneurship, and professional and career development. Transferable skills covered under the TS2 module includes eight topics organized in two sub-groups: (a) Entrepreneurship/Enterprise; and (b) Professional and career development.

This document will also present and review the evaluation of the course by the participant early-stage researchers (ESRs), which will be important in the preparation of the content and preferred type of learning activities for future TS courses namely, namely TS3.

2. Course aims

TS2 is one of three transferable skills modules which jointly aim to foster personal qualities, entrepreneurship and professional career and communication, engagement and impact. TS2 module covered two parts which are guided by the UK Research Development Framework¹:

- Entrepreneurship/Enterprise: knowledge exchange, commercialisation, social enterprise.
- Professional and career development: career management, continuing professional development, responsiveness to opportunities, networking, reputation and esteem.

TS2 has the following learning aims:

1. To develop ESRs' entrepreneurship skills and knowledge of entrepreneurial approaches, ventures and opportunities.
2. To enhance ESRs' professional and career development plans and their effective implementation.

3. Learning outcomes

On the successful completion of the TS2 module, the ESRs were expected to demonstrate the following outcomes:

Entrepreneurship:

- Ability to define basic terms and concepts in the area of entrepreneurship.
- Ability to analyse housing environments in order to identify entrepreneurial opportunities.
- Ability to identify the elements of success of entrepreneurial ventures.
- Knowledge of the basic performance indicators of entrepreneurial activity.
- Ability to evaluate the effectiveness of different entrepreneurial strategies in housing.

Professional and career development:

¹ <https://www.vitae.ac.uk/researchers-professional-development/about-the-vitae-researcher-development-framework>

- Understanding of the connection between effective career/major exploration and the achievement of personal, professional, and academic goals.
- Ability to identify resources for researching majors, careers, internships, and employment.
- Ability to identify potential career areas and majors that reflect own values and interests.
- Ability to identify and pursue employment opportunities (networking, resume-writing, and interviewing).
- Ability to develop a preliminary career plan.

4. Course structure

Figure 1 shows the timeline for the TS2 course, starting in March 2022, and other network activities, as well as the sessions of RMT2 course which ran in parallel to TS2.

Transferable Skills 2 (TS2)

Figure 1. TS2 course structure as integrated with the network activities

Table 1 provides an overview of the programme structure with dates (March-July 2022) and time slots, session titles, brief content descriptions as well as the lead RE-DWELL staff. Further information is provided in Section 5 Learning activities.

Table 1. TS2 session briefs

Date (CET)	Description of activity	Lead (USFD)
01.02.22	TS2 Launch Independent work: Preparation for Workshop session: Entrepreneurship	Karim Hadjri ESRs
30.03.22 Workshop 2	Lectures; hands-on workshop: 1. Content: Entrepreneurship/Enterprise: knowledge exchange, commercialisation, social enterprise. Lecture 1: Entrepreneurship concepts and approaches, by Karim Hadjri (KH) Lecture 2: Entrepreneurship opportunities and ventures, by Krzysztof Nawratek (KN) Lecture 3: Entrepreneurial activity (types and indicators; case studies) (KH/KN) 2. Workshop: How enterprising are you? RDF self-perfection inventory.	Karim Hadjri Krzysztof Nawratek
30.03.22 – 19.05.22	Independent work Task 1: Group work <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exchange of views on the value of entrepreneurship - From PhD research to commercial activity or social enterprise including if possible feedback on lessons learnt from the secondment, internship, employment. Seminar session to present Task 1 on 19.05.22	ESRs
19.05.22	Session 2: Seminar & Task 1 presentation (online) Content: Professional and career development: career management, continuing professional development, responsiveness to opportunities, networking, reputation and esteem. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lecture 1: Professional and career management (KH) Lecture 2: Developing a career plan (structured and unstructured) (KN) Task 1 presentation	Karim Hadjri Krzysztof Nawratek ESRs
19.05.22 – 28.07.22	Independent work Task 2: Group work <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A review of RE-DWELL CDP and the potential doctoral graduate careers that you envisage and why. Seminar session to present Task 2 on 28.07.22	ESRs
15.07.22 Summer School 2	Session 3: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lecture 3: Implementing a career plan (KH/KN) Workshop: CDP overview - doctoral graduate careers. RDF Development Cards. 	Krzysztof Nawratek
28.07.22	Session 4: Task 2 presentation	ESRs

The course was delivered in a blended learning format; a combination of asynchronous and synchronous (on-line and in-person) learning opportunities. This included online lectures, seminars and workshops. In addition, there were in-person sessions during the Workshop in Budapest and the Summer School in Valencia. The course delivery was slightly affected by the Covid-19 pandemic with some colleagues unable to attend some on-site activities. However, course engagement turned out to be very successful. The course delivery was coordinated with colleagues leading RMT2 to avoid session clashes and excessive workload for the ESRs.

TS2 is worth 4 ECTS, approximately 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work (Table 2).

Table 2. Typical TS2 delivery

Events	Course	Workshop 2	Summer School 2
	50 hours (2 ECTS)	25 hours (1 ECTS)	25 hours (1 ECTS)
Online lectures	2	x	x
Online seminars	2	x	x
F2F lectures	x	2	2
F2F workshops	x	2	2
Presentations	6	x	x
Hybrid Panel session	x	x	x
Tutorials	x	1	1
Independent learning (80%)	40	20	20
Actual total hours	50	25	25

There were four main learning components in TS2:

1. On-line lectures
2. On-line seminars and presentations
3. In-person lectures and workshop at WS2
4. In-person lecture and workshop at SS2

These course materials, including recordings, are available in MS Teams:

- Course descriptions
- Recorded Lectures
- Resources
- Sessions
- Tasks

5. Learning activities

TS2 included online lectures and task presentations which took place in March, May and July, and in-person lectures and working sessions during the Workshop in Budapest (March) and the Summer School in Valencia (July).

TS2 training and learning activities were as follows:

5.1. Session 1: Introductory mini-lectures (30.03.22)

The mini-lectures were the first part of the TS2 course and were delivered at the workshop in Budapest. They covered three areas:

1. Entrepreneurship concepts and approaches.
2. Entrepreneurship opportunities and ventures.
3. Entrepreneurial activity (types and indicators; case studies).

Learning aims:

- To develop ESRs' entrepreneurial skills and introduce them to concepts and approaches of entrepreneurship.
- To develop an understanding of entrepreneurship ventures and opportunities.
- To enhance ESRs' awareness of what makes an entrepreneurial activity and what are the key indicators.

Learning outcomes:

- Ability to engage in entrepreneurial activities.
- Awareness of entrepreneurial activities and opportunities.
- Ability to assess an entrepreneurial activity using indicators.

Group learning activities:

- To explore motivation for entrepreneurship.
To discuss the value of entrepreneurial activity.
- To discuss case studies in entrepreneurship.

Group discussions:

- What is entrepreneurship?
- What are the concepts and approaches of entrepreneurship?
- How do you identify entrepreneurial opportunities?
- How do you assess an entrepreneurial activity?
- How enterprising are you?

The sessions used a combination of mini-lectures, a survey and group discussion to answer specific questions related to the topic as illustrated in Figure 2.

The sessions also provided the opportunity to complete and agree on group formation for independent work Task 1.

Figure 2. TS2 Session 1 in Budapest workshop

5.2. Independent work (30.03.22 – 19.05.22)

Task 1: Group work

Task brief: Your views on the value of entrepreneurship - From PhD research to commercial activity or social enterprise including if possible feedback on lessons learnt from the secondment, internship, employment.

Presentation date: 19.05.2022.

5.3. Session 2: Seminar & Task 1 presentation (19.05.22)

The online seminar was delivered synchronously via Teams. It covered two topics:

1. Professional and career management.
2. Developing a career plan (structured and unstructured).

Learning aims:

- To develop ESRs' understanding of professional and career management.
- To develop skills in career planning.
- To enhance ESRs' awareness of career options and pathways.

Learning outcomes:

- Awareness of responsibility for own career development and management.
- Ability to manage own career planning.

Group learning activities:

- To explore career planning and management.
- To discuss career options and pathways.

Group discussion:

- What are your views career development and planning?
- What career options would you consider and why?

During the seminar, ESRs discussed their own career development plan and career objectives. RDF was used to illustrate the various pathways available post-PhD and the need to plan ahead using a robust career plan. Having a CDP will provide a tool for achieving career objectives.

The seminar was followed by group presentations of Task 2. A slide from one of the outputs is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. TS2 Session 2. Group work by Carolina, Anna, Saskia

5.4. Independent work (19.05.22 – 28.07.22)

Task 2: Group work

Task brief: A review of RE-DWELL CDP and the potential doctoral graduate careers that you envisage and why.

Presentation date: 28.07.2022.

5.5. Session 3: Seminar and Workshop (15.07.22)

This session was delivered at the Summer School in Valencia and consisted of a mini-lecture followed by a workshop.

Learning aims:

- To develop skills in career development planning.
- To enhance ESRs' awareness of career opportunities and pathways.

Learning outcomes:

- Ability to engage in career planning and management.
- Awareness of responsibility for own career development.
- Ability to manage own career plan.

Group learning activities:

- Career development planning.
- Implementing a career plan.

Group discussions:

- How do you develop a career plan?
- What are the career options post-PhD?
- Which career pathway you are interested in?

The mini-lecture discussed the implementation of a career plan using the RE-DWELL CDP as an example. It also introduced ESRs to the value of a CDP, its management and implementation.

The seminar led to group activities using the RDF Cards to answer specific questions related to career pathways as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. TS2 Session 3. Workshop activity in Valencia Summer School.

5.6. Session 4: Task 2 presentation (28.07.22)

ESRs were given time to work on Task 2 as a group, and to prepare for their presentations on July 28, 2022. Four groups were created. ESRs were asked to review RE-DWELL CDP and the potential doctoral graduate careers that you envisage and why.

- Group 1's contribution included RE-DWELL timelines for the three ESRs (Androniki, Saskia and Carolina) highlighting key milestones and continuous development. They also mapped their

long-term career vision using the RDF framework. They then overlapped these to identify commonalities which was very helpful (Figure 5).

- Group 2 presented an agenda for career development which highlight research focus, strengths, employment options, what ESRs need to get there, and their position vis a vis the RDF (Figure 6).

- Group 3 discussed transferable skills, reviewed the RDF and mapped their job opportunities. They posited a number of questions using scenarios (with or without a PhD). They also talked about safety nets and job opportunities (Figure 7).

- Group 4 examined the RDF looking at positives and risks, and proposed some suggestions. Each ESR presented a 5-year plan with a research focus. A comparative mapping of career paths and training and skills needed was produced (Figure 8).

Figure 5. Group 1 shared insights

Figure 6. Group 2 shared insights

What if...

Qs

- What is the **alternative to cynical resignation** (the world is unstable, the future looks bleak) on the one hand and **naïve optimism** (I can overcome anything and reach my goals if I just believe in myself) on the other?
- How do we **define success**?
- Is there an **ESR archetype**?
- How do we **develop our self-confidence and enthusiasm** without framing the lack thereof as an **individualised "deficit"**? Can we find a way to nurture these traits in a meaningful way?

Figure 7. Group 3 shared insights

Figure 8. Group 4 shared insights

6. Resources

Resources to support the course were provided via MS Teams folders.

- European Research Council (ERC) (2018) ERC DMP summary document listing FAIR data and resources. DMP online service.
- The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (2018) Eurodoc Report: Identifying Transferable Skills and Competences to Enhance Early-Career Researchers Employability and Competitiveness. Brussels. (Accessed at <http://www.eurodoc.net>)
- Careers Research and Advisory Centre (CRAC) Limited (2010) Researcher Development Framework: Vitae (Accessed at www.vitae.ac.uk/rdf)
- Goodman, A.; Mitchell, A.; Paterman, H. & Shinton, S. (2014) The enterprising researcher: create, recognise and seize opportunities. Published by Careers Research and Advisory Centre. <http://www.vitae.ac.uk/researcherbooklets>
- The Concordat to Support the Career Development of Researchers. September 2019. www.vitae.ac.uk/concordat. www.creativecommons.org.
- Motley, R.J. & McMullin, A. (2020) Developing Your Professional Career Plan. Fam Pract Manag, Jul-Aug; 27(4), 21-24. <https://www.aafp.org/fpm/2020/0700/p21.html>

7. Outputs

ESRs were asked to produce two tasks which led to the following outputs:

Task 1: Group work. Your views on the value of entrepreneurship - From PhD research to commercial activity or social enterprise including if possible feedback on lessons learnt from the secondment, internship, employment. Submission and presentation date on 19.05.2022.

Task 2: Group work. A review of RE-DWELL CDP and the potential doctoral graduate careers that you envisage and why. Submission date on 28.07.2022.

Supervisors' feedback on these two tasks is presented in the annexes.

8. Course evaluation

ESRs evaluated the TS2 course in two contexts: in the Workshop in Budapest, and in the Summer School in Valencia. The highlights of each evaluation are presented next; Annex 3-Evaluation surveys contains the full evaluation results for TS2.

Workshop 2 (Budapest):

The workshop was evaluated by 21 participants through an anonymous online survey. The aim was to evaluate their experience attending the workshop and to identify areas needing improvement. The online survey was completed by 14 ESRs and 7 super-visors/co-supervisors. It included question about the TS2 session (Table 3).

Table 3. Survey results for Workshop 2

Questions	Answers	Supervisors / Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
Please evaluate Transferrable Skills 2 session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	21	4,67	4,21	4,29

Some positive feedback included:

“Very good introduction and well organised and timed”.

“Getting both views of entrepreneurship, a critical and an “encouraging” perspective was well rounded. Overall, great that this course is geared toward producing a career plan, which may be useful”.

“Interesting topic. Entrepreneurship in the social sector has been getting momentum and is something that we should acknowledge. I am very interested to learn more about it”.

ESR mentioned the following:

“The lectures were very informative. Unfortunately, the online participants could only listen to the people on the podium. Hence, most of the discussions were missed”.

“I like being assigned reading - maybe an extra 10-15 minutes of discussion on the paper would've been good”.

Summer School 2 (Valencia):

The survey was evaluated by 13 participants through an anonymous online survey. The online survey was completed by 10 ESRs and 4 super-visors/co-supervisors. The aim was to evaluate their experience attending the Summer School and to identify areas needing improvements. (Table 4):

Table 4. Survey results for Summer School 2

Questions	Answers	Average
Please evaluate Transferable Skills session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	12	4.58

Some positive comments:

“Really nice way to discuss issues that concern our academic development and the link of our current formation with future opportunities”.

“Good to have a hands-on session together and provide more space for debate/discussion”.

“We had so much fun in this session!! The best way to learn!”

“The activity was remarkably good and engaging, the technique card used was really good”.

There were however some critical comments:

“Interesting, albeit generic workshop on the skills and values necessary to venture beyond academia”.

“Not as useful as it seems on paper. Each person has their own personal skills in terms of carrier development. In practice these skills are transferrable by experience and experience alone”.

Annex 1– Task 1 feedback

Task brief: Your views on the value of entrepreneurship - From PhD research to commercial activity or social enterprise including if possible feedback on lessons learnt from the secondment, internship, employment.

The feedback given to ERS is compiled in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1. Feedback to Task 1

Names	Feedback
Christophe, Effrosyni, Andreas	<p>Statement: A Marie Curie is Marie Curie’s worst nightmare.</p> <p>Qualities of entrepreneur; good intro. and concept definition. Interesting take on how to achieve success. The personal aspects... Useful background info on Marie Curie and what could be her anti-entrepreneurship, bad practice etc. Very creative and engaging approach to the topic. Helpful concluding remarks.</p>
Carolina, Anna, Saskia	<p>What social entrepreneurship can teach us?</p> <p>Helpful definition of social entrepreneurship, social innovation. Ideas and positions are well-presented using call-outs and graphics. Good use of examples and personal experiences; this is a strength within this group. Interesting analysis of values of social entrepreneurship highlighting success and failure, which is in-depth, systematic and very informative; highlight relationship to entrepreneurship (excellent visualisation of data). Impressive presentation. Well done.</p>
Aya, Alex, Tijn	<p>Entrepreneurship out of academic research</p> <p>Global perspective with stories from Africa and Europe, looking at case studies. Interesting visualisation of new lab; helpful resources about this case study. AFRIPads case study on a social enterprise is very interesting but needed more info/discussion. European example on green school run is excellent highlighting link to activism as well. Example on speculative real estate and the intricacies of its financing. Overall a very interesting and diverse range of case studies with helpful insight.</p>
Leonardo, Mahmoud, Marko	<p>Meaning of entrepreneurship, the essentials and its timelessness. Helpful historical insight. Interesting approach to visualising entrepreneurship research and timeline. The types proposed are a strong contribution. The review of relevant literature is also very helpful and impressive. Also the lessons learnt and key points from this review are very useful.</p> <p>The consideration of PhD students in this debate is also very interesting and relevant. The value creation proposal can be key in informing future development. Finally, the example on social value helps situate the topic in a different context and provides some useful case studies, especially the social value bank. Overall, a very impressive and highly informative presentation.</p>
Androniki, Annette, Zoe	<p>Self-reflection. Understanding entrepreneurship, exploitation of research and how this can be achieved. Good use of grant agreement info. Questioning the value of entrepreneurship is very helpful as a starting point. Commercial, social and political approaches identified. The use of a personal lens to explore entrepreneurship is excellent and offers ideas for future initiatives. There is a good use of current activities to reflect on skills, goals and activities, including future employment possibilities. Self-reflection within this group is a strength</p>

and provides very interesting insight into understanding of entrepreneurship, employability and the PhD process. Long-term aims and the potential future vision proposed are also very useful.

Annex 2– Task 2 feedback

Task brief: A review of RE-DWELL CDP and the potential doctoral graduate careers that you envisage and why.

The feedback given to ESRs is compiled in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1. Feedback to Task 2

Names	Feedback
Christophe, Effrosyni, Andreas	Statement: A Marie Curie is Marie Curie’s worst nightmare. Qualities of entrepreneur; good intro. and concept definition. Interesting take on how to achieve success. The personal aspects... Useful background info on Marie Curie and what could be her anti-entrepreneurship, bad practice etc. Very creative and engaging approach to the topic. Helpful concluding remarks.
Carolina, Anna, Saskia	What social entrepreneurship can teach us? Helpful definition of social entrepreneurship, social innovation. Ideas and positions are well-presented using call-outs and graphics. Good use of examples and personal experiences; this is a strength within this group. Interesting analysis of values of social entrepreneurship highlighting success and failure, which is in-depth, systematic and very informative; highlight relationship to entrepreneurship (excellent visualisation of data). Impressive presentation. Well done.
Aya, Alex, Tijn	Entrepreneurship out of academic research Global perspective with stories from Africa and Europe, looking at case studies. Interesting visualisation of new lab; helpful resources about this case study. AFRipads case study on a social enterprise is very interesting but needed more info/discussion. European example on green school run is excellent highlighting link to activism as well. Example on speculative real estate and the intricacies of its financing. Overall a very interesting and diverse range of case studies with helpful insight.
Leonardo, Mahmoud, Marko	Meaning of entrepreneurship, the essentials and its timelessness. Helpful historical insight. Interesting approach to visualising entrepreneurship research and timeline. The types proposed are a strong contribution. The review of relevant literature is also very helpful and impressive. Also the lessons learnt and key points from this review are very useful. The consideration of PhD students in this debate is also very interesting and relevant. The value creation proposal can be key in informing future development. Finally, the example on social value helps situate the topic in a different context and provides some useful case studies, especially the social value bank. Overall, a very impressive and highly informative presentation.

**Androniki, Annette,
Zoe**

Self-reflection. Understanding entrepreneurship, exploitation of research and how this can be achieved. Good use of grant agreement info. Questioning the value of entrepreneurship is very helpful as a starting point. Commercial, social and political approaches identified. The use of a personal lens to explore entrepreneurship is excellent and offers ideas for future initiatives. There is a good use of current activities to reflect on skills, goals and activities, including future employment possibilities. Self-reflection within this group is a strength and provides very interesting insight into understanding of entrepreneurship, employability and the PhD process. Long-term aims and the potential future vision proposed are also very useful.

Annex 3– Evaluation surveys

This annex contains the questions and answers of the evaluation surveys for the course sessions in the Budapest workshop on 30 March 2022 (Table 3.1) and in the Valencia summer school on 15 July 2022 (Table 3.2).

Table 3.1. Feedback to the session in the Budapest workshop

Please evaluate "TS2 Course" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	Briefly explain the reasons for your "TS2 Course" session evaluation
5	The part I participated I think worked very well, trying to find out what is happening. Good communication.
5	Even though the topic in itself represents a culture I wholeheartedly resent (entrepreneurship, entrepreneurs etc), the critical way in which it was approached turned this session into a refreshing discussion.
5	
4	TS2 course was not only interesting, but as well quite fun. The only reason why I will not give him yet the highest grad is because it's not clear to me how we would be more entrepreneurs after this course.
4	
5	Very good introduction and well organised and timed.
4	Getting both views of entrepreneurship, a critical and an "encouraging" perspective was well rounded. Overall, great that this course is geared toward producing a career plan, which may be useful.
5	Easy to digest and pave the way to think beyond the 3 years of RE-DWELL.
4	
4	
3	The lectures were very informative. Unfortunately the online participants could only listen to the people on the podium. Hence, most of the discussions were missed.
NA	NA
4	We need more examples of certain practices.
3	Survey was good, as well as the discussion on micro finance.
4	Personally not a big fan of entrepreneurialism, but I thought Karim and Krzysztof did well offering different perspectives and leaving us space to discuss :)
5	I like being assigned reading - maybe an extra 10-15 minutes of discussion on the paper would've been good.
4	Interesting topic. Entrepreneurship in the social sector has been getting momentum and is something that we should acknowledge. I am very interested to learn more about it.

5	A very useful topic, giving an opportunity to ESRs to look ahead and to evaluate career options, with interesting accompanying activities and quizzes delivered by a highly informed and entertaining duet!
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Table 3.2. Feedback to the session in the Valencia summer school

Please evaluate "Transferrable Skills 2" course (from 1- lowest to 5-highest)	Briefly explain the reasons for your "Transferrable Skills 2" course evaluation
5	Really nice way to discuss issues that concern our academic development and the link of our current formation with future opportunities.
4	
5	Interesting, albeit generic workshop on the skills and values necessary to venture beyond academia
2	Not as useful as it seems on paper. Each person has their own personal skills in terms of carrier development. In practice these skills are transferrable by experience and experience alone.
5	This session was the one freaking me out the most. I felt like it is going to be "you need to dream and change the world and do things no one did before" and this kind of talk. However Nawartek was very realistic and honest give us practical advice on how to be open to different opportunities. It is good to have a plan but it is good also to be flexible.
5	They enjoy and discuss a lot!
	Good to have a hands-on session together and provide more space for debate/discussion.
5	We had so much fun in this session!! The best way to learn!
5	The activity was remarkably good and engaging, the technique card used was really good.
4	We all enjoyed this activity being proposed as a game. We played a role (enterprise, volunteering, public entity) and defined the objectives and tools based on that. The only thing I missed was the connection of the game to our own career plan, but I understand that again, the time was too limited to go in detail of everyone's career objectives at that moment.
	NA
5	
5	Amusing and helpful.
5	Great moment for ESR working on "Employability lens on the Vitae Researcher Development Framework for careers outside academia".